

P-lag ratio analysis for sound pattern detection in time series

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

From stock trends to changes in earth's temperature, data that vary over time are usually represented for exploratory purpose. Many graphs and charts techniques have been developed for this aim. There is still hidden pattern in data we can find by simple outstanding methods, for which many statisticians are not used to. For example, Mark Ballora, an expert on music technology at Pennsylvania State University in State College, uses sonification to create symphonies out of scientific data. In fact, sound patterns is part of data dynamical properties (Masset, 2008). What if we can use simple transformations to reveal sound patterns in our data? The answer is that the dream comes true with p-lag ratio analysis. P-lag ratio technique falls back from Pythagoras earlier works. One of his most important discoveries was that harmonic musical intervals could be expressed by perfect numerical ratios, a finding that led him to the realization that all sensible phenomena follow the pattern of number. We inspire our work from his discoveries and have come across useful findings.

In this paper, we investigate sound patterns in financial historical data. We apply the p-lag ratio transformation to real stocks data and random time series data. The results reveal specific pattern to stocks times series, in contrast to time series generate at random.

2. Aim

Our goal is to find certain features related to sound signals hidden in time series to improve unsupervised machine learning for mixture hidden Markov models (MHMM). MHMM was formulated by van de Pol and Langeheine (1990) as a mixed Markov latent class model and

later generalized to include time-constant and time-varying covariates by Vermunt, Tran, and

Magidson (2008). Our research is an attempt to find covariates which may bring relevant sound pattern information about the series of interest. This leads us to investigate p-lag ratio approach. In this paper, we present only the main principles of p-lag ratio idea, and how to use it to transform time series.

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3. Material and methods

1. Definitions and computation

For a time series process $LR(p) = X_t / X_{t+p}$

where p is the lag order. You will recognize here $LR(1)$ which represent returns values for stock price data. $LR(p)$ quantifies the magnitude of the gap between X_t and X_{t+p} . This of course defined for process for which can not take zero value. The distribution of the p -lag variable depends on the distribution of the process we deal with. Assuming we know the process distribution, some straightforward calculus can lead to it, even if the distribution of the process is not a stationary one.

2. Sound pattern: A main assumption we make for this paper is that a sound pattern is represented by an audio signal. Examples of sound signals are stored into Washington University heart sound samples archives. One of them is plotted below (figure 1):

R), the p -lag ratio variable, $LR(p)$ is computed by

Figure 1: Atrialspatial defect heart sound all six p -lag:.

3.A practical comparison: We do a comparison between p -lag ratio of a random time series generated with an AR (2) model (1253 observations), and the S&P /TSX for daily closing price from august 25, 2012 to august 24, 2017 (1253 observations). The lag order

varies from 1 to 3. The graphs from which we build our comparison are present in results section

4. Selection of lag order: the question of how many lag to consider arise, and how to select significant p-lag ratio variables. The first issue was approached by dealing with prediction window. For example, if your data is daily recorded, and you care about what should happen in next 10 days, extending your screening up to the 10-lag ratio variable is better. The second issue was solved by using extreme grading boosting algorithm (Friedman, 2001) to restrict your feature set to the most important p-lag ratio variables. We compute the p-lag ratio importance for the S&P/TSX with xgboost algorithm in R, with a linear booster, and we plot the output.

4. Results

Comparison between AR (2) and S&P /TSX.

Figure 2 shows significant peaks for the 2-lag ratio variable. The magnitude of the peaks reflect the gap between values generate at random. The range of Y-axis is large in amplitude for all the p-lag ratio variabes computed with the AR (2). But, the S&P/TSX does not behave similarly. Obviously, there is a signal pattern highlighted by the p-lag ratio transformation in figure 3. The data we get is noisy, but at first glance, clearly it is not a white noise, and the magnitude of peaks is not constant at all. The red shaded area highlights significant peaks. The higher the peak is, the more you should pay attention to changes and trend in the data.

Our linear booster parameters in xgboost are $\gamma=0$, $\eta = 0.001$, $\text{subsample}=1$, and $\text{nrounds}=100$. The graph express a whole importance of all six p-lag ratio variables. The graph argue to a whole Importance of the first six lag ratio variables.

5. Conclusions

P-lag ratio is designed to show sound patterns in time series. We find significant difference between p-lag ratio of a random time series, an AR (2), and a real financial time series data, the S&P/TSX. Further analysis were performed about the lag-order importance. We use extreme gradient boosting algorithm, with xgboost package in R, and find significant importance of the first six p-lag ratio variables for the S&P/TSX.

What is next?

We are investigating p-lag ratio variables effectiveness in MHMM in an unsupervised learning context. Another ongoing research is about p-lag ratio variables preprocessing and how they are related to momentum indicators.

6. Keywords

p-lag ratio; signal; sound pattern; time series, feature transformation

Figure 2: AR (2) p-lag ratio graphs, p=1, 2, 3

Figure 3: S&P/TSX p -lag ratio graphs, $p=1, 2, 3$ 1- Thexgboost output for the first six lag ratio variables for the S&P/TSX:

Figure 4: